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An open source, information and learning resource for engineering education in the built environment disciplines

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1 INTRODUCTION

Many research studies have highlighted the benefits of virtual learning environments or laboratories for enhancing the student experience in engineering education (EE) [1]–[3]. Previous research has also found virtual laboratories to be an equally effective method for student learning in comparison to on-campus lectures, with students possessing no prior knowledge of the lab topic still benefiting substantially [4]. The “emerging leaders” in EE are now using open and online e-learning platforms to put the student first, by focusing on “socially-relevant” and personalised projects to contribute to the increasing need for multidisciplinary learning and a global impact [5]. One of the most socially relevant topics in engineering today is the challenge of improving the energy efficiency in our building stock. In Europe, the targets for buildings are very ambitious, with an 80-90% reduction in carbon emissions anticipated by the year 2050 [6]. It is evitable that this target will mean a mass upgrade of the existing building stock through energy efficient retrofitting, in order to bring buildings to nearly zero energy status. For engineering students in this area, there are few well-documented examples of low energy buildings and fewer retrofit examples which could be used for project-based learning (PBL) and self-directed learning (SDL). Students in this area could benefit from a real world application that is supported by data and resourced through an intuitive user interface with demonstrative graphics [7].

This paper outlines the development of an open source, web-based learning resource comprising of an information portal, data portal and interactive app, all based on real data from a live building testbed. The learning and information resource acts as a virtual laboratory and presents interactive high resolution data and information from Ireland's National Building Energy Retrofit Testbed (NBERT). The online suite of tools can be used by educators, anywhere in the world, as a basis for the development of energy models and undertaking analysis of performance in a real world application. The learning resource attempts to streamline the pedagogical style in the classroom, enabling students to engage in the development of energy models and analysis based assessments in an exploratory and more fluid manner, to improve the student learning experience.

2 MOTIVATION AND BACKGROUND

In academic environments there are often many stakeholders, with overlapping roles, at the intersections between stakeholder groups. Figure 1 shows this clearly where some members of individual groups may have two or even three roles within an institution (e.g. a lecturer who is a researcher, or a student who may lecture and also be a researcher simultaneously). The NBERT learning resource (www.nbert.xyz) was created as a result of the need to satisfy the needs of multiple stakeholders. Those who created it had hybrid roles within an institution and therefore had an understanding of the needs of multiple groups simultaneously.

Figure 1: Simple stakeholder relationship in universities and institutions

The initial motivation for the learning resource came about as a result of the need to provide data and information to undergraduate students studying energy modelling modules. This information and data is related to the internal and external data logging systems and building information in the zero2020 building [8]. The modules which were considered to benefit from the learning resource, were all continuously assessed modules with PBL. In these modules, data and information were often needed to create or validate energy models, or to inform the choices made when modelling certain phenomena. Students made multiple requests for data or information from lecturers and often ad-hoc solutions were found each year. This unsystematic process was frustrating for both parties, with data and information being sent time and time again, from different lecturers to different students. From a student perspective this often led to a time-lag in a communication between data and information requests, where

lecturers did not have the time to deliver on these requests quickly. Students often got overwhelmed by the size of the datasets they received, as they often only required a subset of a large dataset. Lecturers wanted to make a system that all students could access, a system which would remove the need for multiple emails and multiple downloads on an annual basis. There was also desire from lecturers to allow students to control an element of their learning when modelling energy systems. The final motivation that led to the creation of the learning resource were the needs of multiple researchers in the department to gain access to data and information for model validation or calibration. Researchers in the built environment or energy modelling area were continually in search of well documented buildings with monitoring systems for both internal and external parameters. In a similar manner to students, researchers often found themselves having to analyse large datasets as no selection functionality was built into the source of the datasets they used. For the purposes of this paper only the student and lecturer perspectives will be discussed from this point onwards, as work on the researcher benefits has been discussed previously [9].

3 CONCEPT AND OBJECTIVES

The initial concept was to develop a cross-module platform for students that all module lecturers can access and use for students. This platform would replace the old delivery system mentioned previously. Designed around four main themes (indicated in Figure 2), the concept was to: reduce the response time between student (S) and lecturer (L), to reduce the size and repetition of data downloads, to add an additional level of self-directed learning (SDL), and to create the change from a cellular to a more centralised approach to data and information management at a departmental level. From a student perspective the concept was developed to: open up communications and enable students to explore data and information, allowing them to select the data they needed and choose some of their learning path.

Figure 2: NBERT learning resource concept, from the existing to the proposed system

The communicative expectation with the platform was that there would be no need for extensive email conversations between students and lecturers. It was also expected that lecturers could manage the datasets more effectively and would be able to work collectively to provide data and information in a coherent, structured way. This was expected to allow lecturers to create additional learning resources and add them to this platform to expand on the learning in class across different modules. Finally, the hope was that this platform could be used outside of the college it was designed for and that it could be provided to any institution in the world. Using these themes, concepts and expectations to guide the delivery of the platform, the following objectives were defined:

1. Provide a publicly accessible source of empirical data from a well-documented low energy building for use in the education of operational building performance and to support the development of students' energy models.
2. Provide a rich source of information for undergraduate and postgraduate research projects in energy and the built environment for Ireland and further afield.
3. As part of a future suite of online building energy education applications, develop an online tool for the assessment of Irish climatic cooling potential of various ventilation strategies and building configurations that rely on untreated outdoor air for their source of cooling.

4 DESIGN AND DESCRIPTION OF THE NBERT LEARNING RESOURCE

3.1 Web platform selection

Based on the above objectives, it was decided to create a website which consisted of: An interactive information portal, an open source data portal, and a set of interactive education apps: (i.e. the climate cooling potential analysis tool). It was seen as

important from the start of the project to balance cost, time, quality and the functionality of the platform. It was also seen as important to select a reproducible template that other educators could use for future applications. For this, a variety of easy to use website templates were reviewed. Squarespace (<https://www.squarespace.com/>) was deemed the best option in balancing all the above qualities for developing the website as it required no prior knowledge of typical web development languages and had an easy to use and flexible template options. Outside of just creating a centralised web-platform, creating a modelling or data analysis page with download and upload functionality would require expertise in typical web development languages (HTML, Javascript, Java etc). To overcome this, web-based applications for both the data portal and climate analysis tool were created using Shiny (<https://shiny.rstudio.com/>). Shiny is a package used with the open source program RStudio (<https://www.rstudio.com/>) which requires no prior knowledge of web development language as long as you have knowledge of R-Language.

3.2 Learning resource tool website layout

Having selected the tools for the project the next phase involved the creation of the website that linked all RShiny applications into a single platform. Figure 3 below shows the main structure of the NBERT website where students can access all interactive apps and information and data portals in a single location. One of the main objectives with the website was to create varying levels of learning with increasing amounts of clicks. There was also an attempt made to create “click space” between basic information and detailed information and downloadable data or information.

Figure 3: Structure of NBERT website

The three main components of the platform; information, data and apps are summarised below in sections 3.3 to 3.5.

3.3 Information portal

The NBERT information portal consists of documents, drawings and building specifications that have been gathered during the design, construction and commissioning of the zero2020 building [8], [10]. The portal has been designed to welcome and direct students, researchers and policy makers, to the information they may need. Table 1 gives an indication as the types of information that are available in the information portal.

Table 1: Detail on the information provided in the NBERT information portal

Type	Details
Building geometry and details	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online images with summary text and downloadable pdf drawings
Material Specs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online overview with downloadable data sheet .pdf documents
Airtightness data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online details • Configuration drawings
Natural ventilation system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online summary
Thermal bridging	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online summary of model outputs
PHPP / NEAP model results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online summary with downloadable schematic drawings, sizing details
Energy and environment systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All publications relating to the testbed research made available • Dedicated section summarising the outcomes from long and short term monitoring campaigns with links to relevant data in the data portal
Publications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Details relating to the design and construction is presented
Performance data	
Timeline of construction	

The information portal contains two different sections; a summary information section and a detailed download section. Within the detailed section students can decide on whether they want to look at; building information, energy systems information, or internal environmental information. In summary, the NBERT information portal allows users to:

- Obtain high resolution data covering all aspects of a low energy building necessary to undertake a number of energy analysis modules and assessments as well as the development of bespoke energy models.
- Learn about the measured performance of a low energy building, its energy systems and the indoor environmental quality. Utilisation of the data in laboratory environments will also support interactive learning regarding the factors affecting energy and environmental performance of the building.

3.4 Data Portal

NBERT has capabilities in monitoring and gathering internal and external parameters from three physical systems; a Building Management System (BMS) a more detailed Internal Environmental Monitoring System and an on-site Weather Station. The data portal contains four years of data from 2013-2016 and there are three main data types: Weather data, internal environmental data and energy data. The NBERT data portal allows users to:

- Select user defined NBERT measurement data in graphical and tabular forms
- Download measurement data in various formats and resolutions
- Upload and compare energy model data to NBERT measurement data online

Figure 4: Structure of NBERT data portal

Before entering the data portal a set of “Terms and Conditions” must be accepted. Once this step is completed users have four main options as is shown in Figure 4. The “About” gives users some background about the data, and it is here that students can check to see if a dataset is complete for a year in a particular time interval, by using the data availability table. The three remaining tabs as part of the “navbar” layout are designed to have a sidebar and a main panel. The sidebar allows users to select the sensors they want to look at and select the time they want to analyse. All changes made in the sidebar are reflected dynamically in any of the main panel options. The “Overview” tab panel gives users an idea of the location, and specification of selected instruments or sensors. The “Data” tab panel allows users to see data in tabulated form and download that data in various formats. The “Visualise and Compare” tab panel uses plotly graphics (<https://plot.ly/>) to visualise all selected sensors in time series format. Another part of this tab allows users to upload the results from their models to compare with the NBERT datasets. A statistical summary of each dataset (user defined and NBERT dataset is also indicated). It is expected that students will use this

functionality to report their results from energy models developed within energy analysis modules.

3.5 VC potential tool

Interactive engineering design and analysis applications also form part of the new online platform. While these are intended to perform a more standalone function than the information and data portal they still form part of the overall portal and will be integrated learning delivery tools for energy modelling and energy analysis modules. The first of these applications that is now available is the Ventilative Cooling Potential Analysis (VCPA) Tool. The VCPA tool was also developed in RShiny. It will be used as a core learning tool for an energy analysis module titled Building Thermal Dynamic Analysis (BTDA) as well as a non-core component of the built environment module titled Building Energy Compliance (BEC). The VCPA tool will be used in class to explore the potential that exists in a local climate to provide low energy passive cooling of a buildings' interior. There exists a potential for direct ventilation from the ambient to cool a building when needed. The extent of this potential is a function of the buildings ability to remove excess heat build-up, the relationship between the ambient temperature and the indoor temperature, the airflow capacity of the ventilation solution and, finally, the required internal conditions for satisfactory thermal environment. The theoretical underpinning of this analysis is not covered here but is openly available [11].

Figure 5: Structure of interactive VCPA tool

The VCPA tool is made up of a number of separate sections that the engineering student can work through and use in their analysis (see Figure 5). The first section in the VCPA tool is the “Building Data” section. Here, the student/user inputs all the required information necessary to estimate the number of useful cooling hours from direct ventilation designs that a particular climate and building configuration will have. This is where a lot of the learning process happens for the student. Knowledge must be developed around each input parameter and why it has an influence on the potential for the climate to provide cooling to the building. This parameter set is used as a training palette through the BTDA module. The student uses the information portal

discussed in section 3.3 to obtain all information necessary to complete a climate cooling potential analysis for the NBERT building as an example in class. The second section is the “Cooling Potential” section. Here, students can select different occupancy rates, climate locations and emissions scenarios. Once the building and climate details have been uploaded and the cooling potential analysis has been completed the student can investigate how different types of ventilation strategies and ventilation openings perform when compared with the required ventilation rates for a building in the “Ventilation” section of the VCPA Tool. Often when energy analysis and design assessments are carried out it is difficult and time consuming for a student to undertake a sensitivity analysis of various model inputs and design characteristics that might influence overall performance. The strengths of the VCPA Tool are that it allows students/users to investigate the effects of a plethora of building parameters, climates, and opening types, both dynamically and quickly. This gives the student the opportunity to consider a ventilation design problem and design a solution, while not getting consumed by first principles.

5 CURRENT INSIGHTS AND FUTURE WORK

While the introduction of the new cross module online data platform is still in its infancy there are already a number of key insights that are worthy of mention. These are summarised below along with key developments that are already identified for future revisions of the learning platform.

4.1 Initial Insights

- RStudio and RShiny are very well adapted to the development of online engineering education apps. Simple design and analysis tools could be developed quite easily directly by undergraduate students or more in-depth version by postgraduates and lecturers. The RStudio suite is also fully open source making it license free and fully accessible.
- It is possible to develop a full online information rich suite without specific expertise in computing science. No HTML or JavaScript was required to develop all aspects of the NBERT portal.
- It is possible to provide a fully open source information set for use by any university in the world. The NBERT portal will be available to any lecturer or educator interested in built environment topics and the development of energy, thermal comfort or internal environment models as well as specific applications like the VCPA tool.

4.2 Future Work

The platform is now in its beta testing phase and it will be formally launched in September 2018. Following initial testing a number of future work items have been identified. These include:

- Development of an online sensitivity analysis function within the VCPA tool
- Development of an online cooling performance challenge for students with student comparisons of proposals. (September 2018)
- Part L building regulations benchmarking of NBERT and uploaded data within the data portal
- Heating degree days tool within data portal

- New interactive apps for building energy modelling, HVAC systems analysis and cleanroom ventilation systems design.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents the concept, design and development of an open source web-based learning and information resource. The work presented highlights the need to create more streamlined cross module data and information management solutions, to improve module delivery in modules related to the built environment disciplines. The education resource created attempts to allow students to select manageable subsets of large datasets and emulates real world scenarios where engineers have to navigate online systems to extract only necessary information. The portal is available to any university course in the world that delivers programs in the built environment and wants to undertake an energy analysis of building energy performance. Publishing data online as open source increases opportunities for collaboration in research and increases the connectivity of the research community.

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